

Correlation Between High-Level and Low-Level Transfer Functions of Induced Lightning Strike Testing

Hugo Tavares¹, Roger Farias², Fernando Cano³, Guadalupe Gutiérrez⁴, Raúl Molero⁵,
Ángel Ramírez Linares⁶

¹Electro-Magnetic Environmental Effects Department at Instituto de Soldadura e Qualidade, ²Intelligent Smart Systems at R&D Instituto de Soldadura e Qualidade ³Lightning Direct Effects area within EME and Antenna Systems Engineering Department at Airbus Defence and Space, ⁴Computational Electromagnetics area within EME and Antenna Systems Engineering Department at Airbus Defence and Space, ⁵EMC Testing Department at Airbus Defence and Space, ⁶Voltage Technological Centre

^{1,2}Av. Prof. Dr. Cavaco Silva 33 - Oeiras, ^{2,3,4}Paseo de John Lennon 2 - Getafe, ⁵C/ Eric Kandel 1 - Getafe
{hvtavares, rlfarias}@isq.pt, {fernando.cano, guadalupe.gutierrez, raul.molero}@airbus.com, angel.ramirez@ffii.es

Keywords: LIE, Coaxial Return, DCI, time domain.

1. ABSTRACT

There are a variety of different tests which can be carried out in order to evaluate the potential effects of a lightning event to an aircraft. High-level current tests are generally useful for assessing the actual damage on structures. One the other hand, low-level tests are the common approach for establishing the transfer functions of the external environment applied on the component to the internal environment resulting on systems provided that non-linear effects are not significant or are controlled and compensated.

In this paper we compare the results obtained in a high level lightning strike testing campaign with the results coming from a low level direct current injection testing campaign both carried out on the same aircraft hybrid cockpit (CFC/metal). The tests results are complemented/compared with simulation activities. Additionally, ad-hoc test set-up were manufactured for each test campaigns and are analysed also in this paper.

2. ACRONYMS AND SYMBOLS

CAD – Computer Aided Design

CFC – Carbon Fibre Composite

CW – Continuous Wave

CRN – Coaxial Return Networkⁱ

DCI – Direct Current Injection

ECF – Expanded Copper Foil

EM – Electro Magnetic

EMH – Electro Magnetic Hazard

FD – Frequency Domain

FFT – Fast Fourier Transform

HL – High-Level

HLFU – High-Level Fast Unipolar

HLSU – High-Level Slow Unipolar

IFFT – Inverse Fast Fourier Transform

LIE – Lightning Indirect Effects

LL – Low-Level

LLFU – Low-Level Fast Unipolar

OC – Open Circuit

SC – Short Circuit

SCD – Superficial Current Densitiesⁱⁱ

TD – Time Domain

VNA – Vector Network Analyser

WP – Work Package

3. INTRODUCTION

Financed under the CleanSky2 initiative [1], the PASSARO project (*caPAbilities for innovative Structural and functional teSting of AeROstructures*) included two WPs with the objective of evaluating the EMH transfer function on a hybrid cabin demonstrator up to 400 MHz. To that end a DCI test campaign was performed under the scope of WP8 exclusively with LL threats. To compare this data applicable to the lightning threat, a HL test campaign exclusively on the TD was additionally performed in the scope of WP6. A general view of this HL test campaign and the activities performed were already described in [2].

This paper is organized as follows. Section 4 briefly describes the hybrid cabin demonstrator under test as well as the corresponding test setup details, including the analysis of the input impedances obtained with each CRN. Section 5 summarises the results obtained during the LL test campaign and Section 6 those from the HL test campaign. Section 7 includes the comparison analysis of relevant results from LL and HL tests. Finally, Section 8 presents a summary of the most important conclusions of this work.

4. CABIN DEMONSTRATOR AND TEST SETUP

4.1 Description of the demonstrator

The test object is a hybrid CFC/aluminium cockpit shown on the figure below.

ⁱ CRN and (coaxial) return are used interchangeably.

ⁱⁱ The term current density will be used throughout the text.

Fig. 1 Skin points used for SCD measurements (top and left).

The cabin skin was sampled in 16 points divided over different cabin materials at approximately symmetrical positions on the longitudinal plane as shown on Fig. 1 for the characterization of the SCD induced on the skin due to the external threat. Inside the cabin, a test harness was fitted on the topmost areas, as illustrated on Fig. 2, based on aerospace grade over braid, where inner circuits with different types of terminations were fitted.

Fig. 2 CAD overlay of the top harness.

Its inner circuits are represented on Fig. 3, which show circuits in 50 Ω, OC and SC terminations inside each load box where measurement instrumentation was installed and shielded.

Fig. 3 Top harness description.

4.2 LL CRN Configuration

Two different topologies of CRN's were used for the purpose of LL or HL tests. The CRNs are defined as coaxial as possible to minimise its influence on the current distribution as required by the LIE standards [4]. The first CRN, shown on Fig. 4, was dedicated to LL tests where frequencies up to 400 MHz were used. It was based on a construction of 40 stranded copper wires with 6 mm² cross section. The EM CAD model used for simulations is illustrated on Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 Physical CRN used on the LL DCI measurements.

This CRN was designed to keep a nearly constant distance from the cabin skin to the CRN wires of approximately 45 cm. On the transversal plane the widest distance between wires was kept at 40 cm and the minimum clearance to the ground plane from the bottom wires was 25 cm.

Fig. 5 CAD model of the LL DCI setup.

4.3 HL CRN Configuration

The second topology, dedicated to HL tests, was only used to apply lightning pulses with significant frequencies below 1 MHz. It is substantially different from the LL return due to the laboratory constrains and the significant energy of the threat applied. It's based on a total of 8 copper bands with 110 mm width and 0,5 mm thickness has shown on Fig. 6 and modelled on Fig. 7.

Fig. 6 Physical CRN used on the HL DCI measurements.

Fig. 7 CAD model of the HL DCI setup.

4.4 CRN Input Impedance

On both topologies, the input port was set at the nose of the cockpit and the CRN termination was set at the back of the cockpit. The input impedance of each CRN was measured and validated via simulation. The following figures illustrate the measured and simulated impedances of each CRN when the output port is terminated in SC.

Fig. 8 LL CRN input impedance simulation in SC.

Fig. 9 HL CRN input impedance simulation in SC.

It is evident from this data that there is a good agreement between measurements and simulation on the resonance

frequencies of the LL CRN even though their amplitudes are relatively offset. On the other side, the simulation results obtained for the HL CRN are significantly different especially after the second resonant frequency. In either case, the behaviour of the input impedance is clearly divergent from the measurements above 100 MHz which may be attributed to the EM model design parameters of the CRN elements (further investigation would be required to confirm this behaviour). Considering the frequency content of the waveforms under study in this paper, the agreement between measurements and simulation is acceptable.

4.5 External Threats and Post-Processing

4.5.1 Reference External Threats

The evaluation of the cockpit internal electromagnetic environment is performed by injecting either a TD current pulse (on both CRN configurations) or a swept CW source (only on the LL CRN). Regardless of the type of excitation, the objective is to characterize the SCD and the induced currents on the internal harness looms and circuits. The waveforms defined in [3] have been considered as a reference for these tests.

The later analysis presented in Section 7 of this paper, is focused on results obtained from TD unipolar waveforms, (with amplitude and timing parameters specified on Table 1) used during the LL and HL test campaigns. The LLFU is a low amplitude fast waveform used on the LL CRN. The HLFU is a high amplitude fast waveform used on the HL CRN for comparison. Finally, the HLSU is a high amplitude waveform with a lower frequency content (when compared with the LLFU and HLFU) for the purposes of comparing the dependence on the system response versus threat frequency content.

Table 1 Timing characteristics of unipolar threat currents.

Waveform	Risetime ⁱⁱⁱ / peak time/ duration, μ s	Current peak
LLFU	3.4 / 7.0 / 72.2	323 A
HLFU	6.2 / 10.1 / 17.6	50 kA
HLSU	22.2 / 36.3 / 92.7	50 kA

When swept sources are used for the purpose of LL FD tests, the CRN output port is matched to the impedance of the VNA. On all TD tests, the output port is terminated in SC.

4.5.2 Induced Currents and SCD Calculation

Loom currents and their inner circuit currents are measured by magnetic sensors (on LL tests) or Rogowski coils (on HL tests). Filtering and integration were required to obtain the reference data for subsequent analysis (integration) on the case of currents measured with Rogowski coils.

The SCD's are measured by B-Dot probes which respond to the derivative of $H(t)$ as described by (1), where A_{eq} is the equivalent area of the sensor and μ_0 the permeability of free space. A calculation example is shown on Fig. 10 and Fig. 11.

$$v(t) = A_{eq} \mu_0 \frac{dH(t)}{dt} \quad (1)$$

⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾ Unless otherwise noted throughout the paper, rise times are considered between 10 % and 90 % and duration times at 50 % of peak levels.

Fig. 10 Example of TD measured B-Dot voltage for the LLFU threat.

Fig. 11 Numerically integrated peak SCD.

5. TEST IN LOW-LEVEL

It is important to note that the measured data presented on this section was obtained with the CRN in SC for the comparison with the HL data presented in Section 6 and with the CRN terminated in 50Ω for comparison with the FD data presented on Section 5.2.

5.1 Low-Level Test in TD

5.1.1 Applied threat

The threat considered for the measurements presented on this section is referenced by LLFU on Table 1. For these measurements, the CRN was terminated in SC. The figure below illustrates a typical LLFU threat.

Fig. 12 Typical LLFU current threat used on the LL test campaign.

5.1.2 Surface Current Densities Obtained with LL CRN

The following table summarizes some of the measurements and simulations performed on this configuration. On the line referenced “meas” the measured longitudinal SCD values are presented; it’s rise, and peak times are shown by t_r and t_p respectively. Finally, the line with “sim” refers to the longitudinal SCD values obtained by simulation. Skin points are on the table columns (L=Left, R=Right, B=Bottom and T=Top) followed by an integer with the point number (refer to Fig. 1). Unfortunately, the number of measured points was low; therefore, simulations were performed to sample the expected SCD on the remaining points of the cabin skin for comparison.

Table 2 SCD response to the LLFU threat.

Point	L1	R1	T1	B1	B3	R2	T3	L4
meas	54	53	49	-	-	-	-	-
$t_r, \mu s$	3.5	3.5	3.5	-	-	-	-	-
$t_p, \mu s$	8.1	8.0	8.1	-	-	-	-	-
sim	61	57	53	74	57	55	39	65

Theoretical calculations assuming a homogeneous and infinite wire using (2), where P_{eff} is the effective perimeter over the cockpit skin, yield peak SCD’s for point T1 of 60.3 A/m (assu-

$$H(t) = \frac{I(t)}{P_{eff}} \quad (2)$$

ming an effective perimeter of 536 cm), and, for points L1 and R1, a peak SCD of 64 A/m (assuming an effective perimeter of 508 cm). Measurements and simulations show equivalent results in the sense that points L1 and R1 yield slightly higher peak SCD’s when compared to point T1.

The data obtained from the simulation yield very comparable values with the measurements. In fact, for the points T1, R1 and L1 variations between simulation and measurements are only up to 13 %. It is important to note that, despite being longitudinally symmetrical, points L1 and R1 have slightly different peak SCD’s on the simulation results. This variation is believed to be due to the positioning of the probe point relative to the mesh of the model parts used for integration.

For the remaining points and considering only the data provided by simulation, it’s noticeable that points located closer to the bottom of the cabin yielded higher peak SCD’s when compared with topmost points. This can be seen comparing the amplitudes for points B1 and B3 with R2 and R3. As an outlier, the value obtained for L4 cannot be easily justified and requires further investigation since it is located over the largest perimeter of the cockpit.

Finally, regarding the timing response of the SCD’s, both measurement and simulation have followed closely the external threat timing. In fact, from the timings provided on Table 2 for the measured data, we can see the rise time matches very well for all points ($3.4 \mu s$ to $3.4 \mu s$) and the peak time also follows closely the external threat timing ($8.1 \mu s$ to $7.0 \mu s$). For the simulation data, peak times in the order of $7.2 \mu s$ and rise times of $3.3 \mu s$ have been found as shown on Fig. 13.

Fig. 13 SCD peak/rise time response for the simulated LLFU threat.

5.1.3 Looms Response to the Fast Unipolar Threat

The induced currents obtained with the LL return are shown on Table 3. The line with “meas” represents the peak induced current on each loom (LTB1 at the input of box Top 1; same for the other boxes). The rise time and peak time of the induced currents are shown on lines t_r and t_p respectively.

Table 3 Induced currents obtained for the LLFU threat.

Loom	LTB1	LTB2	LTB3	LTB4
meas, A	1.27	1.92	3.04	0.12
$t_r, \mu s$	17.6	17.4	17.2	5.1 / -
$t_p, \mu s$	29.5	31.3	30.8	9.5 / 106.4
Ratio, A/kA	3.9	5.9	9.4	0.4
sim, A	1.48	2.0	2.89	0.65

The induced current levels range up to 3 A for a peak total injected current of 323 A. In addition, it is evident the substantial dispersion observed in both the rise-time (from 3.4 μs of the injected current threat to values in the order of 17 μs for the induced current) and peak-times are further delayed from 7 μs to nearly 30 μs .

This behaviour is not followed for the induced current on harness LTB4. This section of the harness is primarily routed perpendicular to the lightning current flow on the structure from one side to the other – right to left. The induced value is very low as expected for a perpendicular harness. The response seems to be a superposition of two double exponential signals, one faster and higher in peak amplitude than the other. The faster signal seems to approximate the parameters of the injected current with a rise time of 5.4 μs and a peak time of 9.5 μs for the higher and faster peak (which are closer to the timing parameters of the LLFU current threat of Table 1) and 106.4 μs for the slower subsequent peak.

Fig. 14 Typical response of the induced current on LTB4.

Finally, one note regarding the values obtained for the HLFU simulations. The peak induced values obtained for looms LTB1, LTB2 and LTB3 correlate very well with the measured values. However, the peak value obtained for loom LTB4 are significantly offset. We suspect this is due to a less effective simplification of the EM CAD model on the transversal section where this section of the harness is deployed.

5.2 Low-Level Test in FD

5.2.1 Applied Threat

To perform the FD analysis, the results from a LL DCI test campaign performed in the FD were used as a reference for comparison with the data in TD presented on the previous section. The FD data was obtained with the CRN output port in 50 Ω to improve the impedance match of the test instrumentation. On this configuration the timing characteristics are equivalent to those of Table 1 but peak injected current is reduced to about 29 A. With the frequency domain data, and after performing appropriate IFFT/FFT post-processing, it's possible to obtain the TD equivalent results to the injected waveform LLFU threat of Table 1 in TD.

The following figures show the results of the post-processing for the loom currents on harness LTB2 and LTB3. As can be seen, the resulting post-processing approaches quite well in terms of peak amplitude and timing characteristics the induced current measured on the TD.

Fig. 15 Resulting FD to TD LL post-processing for loom current LTB2.

Fig. 16 Resulting FD to TD LL post-processing for loom current LTB3.

5.3 Comparison of results from FD and TD

The results described on Section 5.1 for the LL threat in the TD and on Section 5.2 for the transformation from the FD to the TD show that the FD measurements may be enough to perform a later assessment via post-processing for threats on the TD. This results on a substantial shortened test campaign, with measurements only performed on the FD, and validates one the objectives of the PASSARO project regarding the equivalence of FD and TD measurements.

6. TEST IN HIGH-LEVEL

6.1 Applied Threat

As already anticipated in Section 4, the data and analysis included in this paper are focused on the HL unipolar waveforms applied during the test campaign (additional data and analysis of other waveforms was already presented in [2]). The figure below illustrates to scale both the fast (HLFU) and slow (HLSU) threat currents used for testing referenced on Table 1.

Fig. 17 Unipolar threats at a nominal level of 50 kA.

6.2 SCD Response to the Fast-Unipolar Threat

Table 4 summarizes the SCD response for the HLFU threat of Table 1 with a nominal level of 50 kA. The SCD data shows the longitudinal and transversal component of the measured SCD ($meas_L$ and $meas_T$ respectively), rise and peak times. Finally, the longitudinal component of the simulated SCD, sim_L is shown.

Table 4 SCD's obtained for the HLFU threat.

Superficial peak current densities $H_p(t)$, kA/m						
Point	L3	L4	T1	T3	R3	B3
$meas_L$	3.6	4.4	8.6	7.9	2.4	7.4
t_r , μs	6.1	6.1	6.5	5.6	6.5	6.0
t_p , μs	11.2	11.0	12.1	9.9	11.5	10.4
$meas_T$	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2
sim_L	3.1	8.8	14.6	9.3	3.1	17.2

Following the same rationale of Section 5.1.2 regarding the theoretical expected peak SCD, the measured value expected for point T1 should be circa 9.3 kA/m (8 % higher than the measured value). For all other points, which have nearly identical effective perimeters circa 800 cm, the measured peak SCD value decreases as expected with the increase of the perimeter at this transversal plane. The value obtained for points T3 and B3 show however a peak value higher than expected (by about 30 %). It should be noted that one possible explanation for this deviation is the fact that since the CRN termination is made directly to the back cover of the cockpit, an increase on current density on these areas is also expected.

Unlike the data of Table 2 where very low dispersion of rise times was observed, the integration of the derivative signal on the HL measurements shows a wider dispersion of the resulting rise times (from 5.6 to 6.5 μs) but also the peak times (9.9 to 12.1 μs). Regardless, the rise times and peak times for the computed SCD still follow consistently the behaviour of the injected current threat as expected. The values observed

for the transversal component of the SCD are nearly two orders of magnitude smaller than those observed for the longitudinal component. These figures are validated by simulations that show even smaller values. This apparent discrepancy between simulation and measurement may be due to positioning error of the probe on the cabin skin measuring low signal-to-noise signals.

Comparing the simulated values for the HLFU threat configuration, we can conclude they generally follow the behaviour of the measured data. Notable exceptions seem the fact that the peak SCD value for points T1, L4 but especially B3 are clearly exacerbated compared with the measured values. Verifications into this apparent discrepancy are taking place with an eventual EM model optimization required.

Finally, the timing characteristics of the simulated SCD matches well those of the external threat. The figure below illustrates the TD response obtained for points L4 and R3 as an example.

Fig. 18 SCD peak/rise time response for the simulated HLFU threat.

6.3 Looms Response to the Fast-Unipolar Threat

The figure below illustrates the normalized induced currents on the loom due to the HLFU threat at a level of 50 kA. The data on Table 5 summarizes the relevant parameters of the current induced on each loom. Rows with "meas" report the peak induced current; rise time and peak time are indicated by t_r and t_p , respectively. The "ratio" represents the peak measured current normalized by the injected threat current.

Fig. 19: Loom response to the HLFU threat.

Table 5: Induced currents obtained for the HLFU threat.

Loom	LTB1	LTB2	LTB3	LTB4
meas, A	171.2	223.1	384.2	5.4
$t_r, \mu s$	11.3	10.3	11.4	4.8
$t_p, \mu s$	20.1	17.8	19.9	9.2
ratio, A/kA	3.5	4.6	7.9	0.1
sim, A	226.0	232.2	356.0	108.4
ratio, mA/A	4.5	4.6	7.1	2.1
$t_r, \mu s$	11.6	11.5	11.6	11.1

Unlike the LL induced loom currents, the loom currents in HL were measured with Rogowski probes. It's noticeable an increase on the rise time and time to peak observed on looms LTB1, LTB2 and LTB3 when compared with the timing characteristics of the HLFU threat specified on Table 1. This behaviour was already observed on the LL results presented on Section 5.1.3. In fact, induced currents on looms LTB1 to LTB3 reach the peak value substantially after LTB4, which exhibit the same double exponential response as described in the LL threat. Looms LTB1 to LTB3 peak at about 20 μs when the threat peak time is at 10 μs .

Regarding the simulated induced values, amplitudes obtained for LTB1, LTB2 and LTB3 are within acceptable tolerance when compared with the measured data. However, the values obtained for LTB4 is significantly off. It is interesting to note that such a large offset was already observed on the LLFU results previously described on Section 5.1.3. This seems to validate the fact that a relevant factor on the EM model is affecting the simulation results for this loom. Finally, it is interesting to note that the rise time of the simulated data follows the timings of the measured data, this confirming the delay in the peak instant of the induced currents.

6.4 Looms Response to the Slow-Unipolar Threat

The induced loom currents response to the HLSU threat of Table 1, are summarized on Table 6 for a threat level of 50 kA; the TD response is illustrated on Fig. 20.

Comparing the induced peak current values obtained for both the HLFU and HLSU threats, on Table 5 and Table 6 respectively, it's noticeable that the lower frequency threat has coupled to the internal environment more effectively since the induced peak values are clearly higher for the HLSU threat. This may be mainly associated to the response of the wiring harness overbraid's impedance (high inductance and low resistance) when compared to the skin impedance (low inductance and mid resistance). In fact, induced peak values have increased between 65 % and 80 % relative to the levels of the HLFU threat for the same loom. This clearly indicates the dependence on the coupling effectiveness as a function of the bandwidth (rise time) of the threat current.

Table 6: Induced currents obtained for the HLSU threat.

Loom	LTB1	LTB2	LTB3	LTB4
meas, A	311.4	368.4	687.6	4.2
$t_r, \mu s$	30.8	30.2	31.1	-
$t_p, \mu s$	53.4	51.4	53.5	10.3 / 156.7
ratio, A/kA	6.3	7.4	13.8	0.2

Furthermore, it's important to note the substantial delay on the threat current response timings. Loom peaks occur between 51.4 μs for loom LTB1 and 53.5 μs for loom LTB3 when the HLSU threat current peaks at about 36 μs . Loom LTB4 shows again a faster response peaking first at approximately 10.3 μs .

However, the last and highest amplitude peak occurs much later at around 156.7 μs .

Fig. 20: Loom response to the HLSU threat.

6.5 Circuits Response to the Slow-Unipolar Threat

An assessment of the electromagnetic coupling into the harness is not complete without presenting an example of the coupling into the harness inner circuits. The circuits voltages measured on box Top 2 are illustrated on Fig. 21 and summarized on Peak voltage, and as on the previous sections, is followed by the rise time and peak time of the measured voltage. Finally, the "ratio" represents the normalized induced voltage to the injected current threat.

Table 7. Row "meas" represents the measured

Fig. 21: Inner circuits response to the HLSU threat.

Peak voltage, and as on the previous sections, is followed by the rise time and peak time of the measured voltage. Finally, the "ratio" represents the normalized induced voltage to the injected current threat.

Table 7: Induced circuit voltages obtained for the HLFU threat.

Loom	Circuit 1	Circuit 4	Circuit 5
meas, V	0.8	8.2	5.9
$t_r, \mu s$	13.0	30.7	30.6
$t_p, \mu s$	20.2	53.4	46.7
ratio, mV/kA	16	164	119

These results allow to draw some interesting conclusions. First the peak disturbance value of 0.8 V observed for Circuit 1. This circuit is laid over a fully metallic section of the nose. However, circuit's 4 and 5, have a significant length laid over CFC and CFC+ECF sections of the skin. Not only these circuits exhibit higher peak induced voltage due to the structural RI voltage drop on the composite section of the cabin (values in the order of 8 V when compared to 0.8 V on circuit 1), but they also peak later (around 30 μs later

compared to Circuit 1). Second, and considering the total length of the cabin and the length exclusively constructed of composite materials we can roughly estimate a voltage drop in the order of 2.9 V/m of fuselage length, which is considerable for longer airframes. Finally, it's worth noting the peak value of the peak induced voltage for circuit 4 and 5. circuit 4 is effectively longer than circuit 5, and in addition a substantial length is laid on a transversal direction of the cabin. However, the reference ground for this circuit incorporates a smaller length of CFC hence the reason the peak value for circuit 5 is slightly lower than Circuit 4.

7. COMPARISON OF RESULTS FROM LL AND HL TESTS

It is important to note that all the measured TD data presented throughout the paper, does not consider any mismatch effect due to the combination of the impedance presented to the generators and amplifiers used during the test campaign. Therefore, this factor should be considered as a possible source of error and uncertainty on the measured data provided on this paper.

7.1 Superficial Current Densities

Compiling the data from Table 2 and Table 4 we can summarize the peak SCD's for the LLFU and HLFU threats. This table summarizes the ratio of peak SCD to the injected threat level.

Table 8: Summary of normalized peak SCD's.

Point	Peak normalized SCD's - [A/m] / A							
	T1	L1	R1	B3	T3	L3	R3	L4
LLFU	0.15	0.15	0.16	<i>0.23</i>	<i>0.17</i>	-	-	<i>0.2</i>
HLFU	0.17	-	-	0.15	0.16	0.07	0.05	0.09

Points are ordered from left to right, with increasing distance from the skin to the axis of injection (increased effective perimeter), even though the variation from point B3 to the right is relatively small for the skin to axis of injection distance. Unfortunately, there is not enough data to perform a clear comparison for each threat based on measured values. Data in italic is based on the simulation results of Table 2. In any case the data seems to suggest as expected theoretically, a larger normalized peak SCD towards the frontmost points on the cabin skin, up to point R1. For instance, even though point T1 is located over aluminium, the peak SCD's are very similar (0.15 vs 0.17) for the two different threats. Note that, to the points to the right of point R1, all points are over a CFC and/or a CFC+ECF skin. Starting at point L3, the peak SCD's diminish vastly where a larger increase of distance (perimeter) is observed.

The peak values obtained for points B3 and T3 are more difficult to justify. The normalized value obtained for T3 is nearly identical between LLFU and HLFU configurations. However, for B3 there is an appreciable difference between measurement and simulation. Most important is the fact that these values should have shown a decay relative to the value of the frontmost points. In any case, for either CRN configuration, this seems to suggest a SCD enhancement on the bottommost points as already analysed.

Finally, and as expected, the SCD's rise-time and peak time follow closely the waveshape of the injected threat in either case of the LLFU and HLFU threat.

Additional simulation activities have been performed with the purpose of evaluating the potential effects of the different CRN's on the homogeneity of the SCD over the cockpit skin. For this purpose, additional SCD probes have been inserted over the cabin skin between adjacent straps at a defined transversal plane. Results have shown that there is a significant variation between points directly under the straps and points adjacent to the straps on the 8 band CRN configuration. On the other hand, the results of the 40 wire CRN configuration have shown a very good homogeneity.

7.2 Induced Currents

The following table summarizes the normalized induced currents on the looms for the LL and HL threats from Table 3, Table 5 and Table 6, for the LLFU, HLFU and HLSU threats respectively.

Table 9: Normalized induced current response to the LL and HL threats.

	LTB1	LTB2	LTB3	LTB4
LLFU - mA/A	3.9	5.9	9.4	0.4
HLFU - mA/A	3.5	4.6	7.9	0.1
HLSU - mA/A	6.3	7.4	13.8	0.2

Considering as a closer reference to the real values the data for the LLFU, all looms except LTB4 fall within an acceptable range. In fact, values in the range up to 10 mA/A were obtained for all looms except for LTB4 which shows induced levels more than one order of magnitude less. This loom is bonded to a slightly forward position of LTB3 (refer to Fig. 3) - approximately to a length of 26 cm. In addition, the longer part of loom LTB4 is deployed transversally to the cabin. Hence, a residual induction level was obtained as expected at this loom as reported on Sections 5.1.3, 6.3 and 6.5.

It should be noted from Fig. 2, that a substantial part of the top harness is extremely exposed to the penetrating lines of the magnetic field from the apertures of the windshield. However, loom LTB3 has the highest value. This should be because the farthest exit point is fact the bonding strap of box LTB3. Therefore, the current exiting from LTB3 should approximate the currents entering the internal environment through LTB1 and LTB2 since LTB4 is neglectable. In fact, a thorough analysis of both LL and HL induced waveforms validates the entry point for the induced currents on the top harness (LTB1 and LTB2) as well as their exit from the looms to the cabin skin via LTB3. However, when comparing with normalized induced currents of the faster waveforms, LLFU and HLFU, with the slower threat waveform, HLSU, we can observe values up to 80 % higher for the slower threat waveform, except for LTB4 for reasons already analysed on previous sections. Unfortunately, data is scarce to suggest any effect of the CRN on this slower threat for the SCD behaviour.

When comparing the normalized induced peak currents for the LL and HL threats we can conclude that the values obtained for the HLFU are similar to those obtained for the LLFU. It indicates that non-linear effects are not significant, as already discussed in [2], at least up to the level tested. Regarding the variability between both results, the two main contributors identified are: the small differences between LL and HL injected waveforms and the effect of the different CRN used on each test. This seems to confirm that the different CRN used for LLFU and HLFU campaigns configurations does not show significant effect on the harness induced current values

(even when the SCD distribution is not perfectly homogeneous as discussed on the previous section).

However, comparing the response of the system to the fast unipolar waveforms (LLFU and HLFU) with that of the HLSU, the coupled values are significantly increased (up to 80 % higher peak current values). This behaviour may be explained by the balance between the frequency dependent impedance of the skin, harness impedance, and threat bandwidth on the hybrid composite/metal cockpit structure.

A further comparison on the TD can be made. The figure below illustrates in blue the LL transformation of the current threat HLFU. The peak levels compare reasonably well (approximately 170 A for the HL and 140 A for the LL). Also, the rise time and peak time match relatively well the HL original response on the TD.

Fig. 22: HL vs LL TD comparison for LTB1.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a brief characterization of the internal electromagnetic environment of a hybrid cockpit demonstrator. Measurements and simulations have been performed in both the TD and FD for external threats of LL and HL. However, the optimization of simulation results is ongoing due to some discrepancies found and explained throughout the paper. Two different CRN topologies were considered for evaluation. The data presented on this paper for the SCD's and induced loom currents, seem to suggest the LL CRN (40 wires) results in a very homogenous distribution of the SCD, while the HL CRN (8 copper band) shows concentration of the SCD in the areas behind the return conductor. On the other hand, it seems to not have a major effect on the currents induced on internal harnesses.

The simulations and measurements have been performed to assess the CRN input impedance, showed no relevant oscillations up to 2 MHz, since the power density spectra of the threats considered is largely below 2 MHz (at least 60 dB below peak levels).

One lesson learn to highlight is that it is very important to define adequate location and installation of the SCD probes in order to obtain adequate and comparable data. It is advisable to avoid local effects such as those produced by the close proximity to the cockpit-CRN interface.

The FD domain analysis of the LLFU showed that it is possible to approach the analysis of the lightning threat by using the source data provided by a FD DCI and applying IFFT/FFT post-processing.

Data on the current coupled on harnesses showed quite good correlation between LLFU and HLFU TD results even when different CRNs were used for each test and it has a significant effect on the SCD distribution. Therefore, non-linear effects seems to be also not very significant.

On the other hand, it is observed an appreciable difference between normalized peak induced current levels when comparing results from the LLFU/HLFU with those from the HLSU as well as a significant difference also on their timing characteristics, having observed important delays on the induced currents for the HLSU. This is evident for the normalized induced currents and partly observable on the peak normalized SCD's, suggesting an effect may exist on the later.

When applying the HLSU threat to the cockpit, the induced levels on internal harness are higher when compared with those obtained with HLFU. The energy content of the HLSU waveform is primarily at lower frequency bandwidth, therefore, considering the impedance of the harness (high inductance and low resistance), the coupling mechanism for such waveform seems more effective. Not only a substantial increase on the normalized peak loom currents is observed but also similar results are observed also when analysing results from internal wiring. In fact, the effect of the structural voltage drop due to the finite conductivity of the CFC parts of the cabin can be seen on the loom circuits with OC terminations. It was possible to estimate voltage drops of about 2.9 V per meter of cabin length for threat levels of 50 kA.

Therefore, from the three different threats considered, the data presented on this paper suggests that the timing characteristics of the external threat (its frequency content), influence significantly the levels on the internal electromagnetic environment of the cabin.

An interesting behaviour was observed on loom LTB4. The response on this loom appears as a combination of two signals for the LLFU and HLFU threats. The faster signal could be attributed to the fact that a substantial part of this loom is actually deployed transversally along a frame, with an estimated length of 4,44 m under the skin material of CFC and CFC+ECF (refer to the node connecting box Top 3 and Top 4 and respective layout on Fig. 2, Fig. 3 and Fig. 1). The slower part follows the same response as the other looms.

9. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present work was funded by the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research programme under Grant agreement No 807083, to which the authors would like to express their acknowledgement.

10. REFERENCES

- [1] <http://passaro.inegi.up.pt/index.asp>
- [2] F. Cano, J. García, J. Menéndez, H. Tavares, A. Khamlichi, A. Ramírez, A. Fernández and C.L. Aguilar, "Lightning Test on a Full Scale Hybrid (Composite-Metal) Demonstrator Cockpit with Integrated Structural Health Monitoring Systems", ICOLSE 2019.
- [3] EUROCAE ED-84, "Aircraft Lightning Environment and Related Test Waveforms Standards", July 2013.
- [4] EUROCAE ED-107A, "Guide to the Certification of Aircraft in a High-Intensity Radiated Field (HIRF) Environment", July 2010